
Interview Protocol: Phase 1 Practitioner Verification

DPP Interoperability Platform — Practitioner Validation

Jorge Renato Leon Chumpitaz
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam / Universiteit van Amsterdam
MSc Computer Science — Software Engineering for Green Deal

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Methodology	Semi-structured interviews following DSR evaluation guidelines (Hevner 2004; Peffers et al. 2007)
Participants	3–5 practitioners from DPP initiatives, standards bodies, or industry implementers
Duration	50–55 minutes per interview (two protocols in one session)
Structure	Protocol 1 (Schema & Data Model, ~25 min) + Protocol 2 (Adoption & Implementation, ~25 min)
Revision note	v3.0 incorporates feedback from test interview (Feb 24): adaptive questioning, simpler language, explicit handout navigation, knowledge-gauging warm-up, realistic timing

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1 Interview Design

1.1 Objectives

This interview protocol validates the DPP Interoperability Platform through two complementary protocols conducted in a single session:

Protocol 1 — Schema & Data Model Validation addresses **SQ2** (core-extension boundary for product-agnostic schema) and **SQ3** (transformation fidelity with provenance and gap reporting):

1. **Core schema boundary:** Is the v0.2 minimal core (17 product-agnostic fields) appropriate, or should fields be added or removed?
2. **Extension architecture viability:** Does the core + extensions model (battery, SoC, LCA-EF, food) align with industry needs?
3. **Provenance and trust:** Do per-field provenance and gap reporting meet stakeholder auditability requirements?

Protocol 2 — Adoption & Implementation Evaluation addresses **SQ1** (identifier resolution across heterogeneous ID standards), **SQ4** (JSON-LD feasibility for semantic interoperability), and **SQ5** (practitioner validation of usability and completeness):

1. **Adoption barriers and enablers:** What practical challenges exist for DPP data exchange, and what would enable adoption?
2. **Implementation assessment:** Through a live demonstration, does the platform meet practitioner expectations?
3. **Pilot readiness:** What acceptance criteria would give this platform a viable path to real-world deployment?
4. **Missing requirements:** Are there critical requirements for DPP interoperability not yet addressed?

1.2 Participant Selection Criteria

Criterion	Rationale
Domain expertise in DPP implementation or standards	Ensures feedback grounded in practical experience
Familiarity with at least one initiative (Tractus-X, Battery Pass, CIRPASS, UNTP)	Enables concrete assessment of adapter mappings
Mix of technical and business roles	Balances technical feasibility with business relevance
No prior involvement in this thesis project	Avoids bias and insider knowledge effects

Table 1: Participant selection criteria

1.3 Adaptive Interview Guidance

Lessons from Test Interview (Feb 24)

A test interview with a colleague (55 min) identified key improvements:

1. **Start high-level, zoom in gradually.** Many questions assumed domain expertise the participant did not have. Begin with open questions, then narrow based on responses.
2. **Gauge knowledge first.** Ask what the participant knows about DPPs and which aspects they focus on *before* asking schema-specific questions.
3. **Navigate the handout explicitly.** Always point to the exact section and page when asking a question. Say “please look at Section 4 of your handout” rather than assuming familiarity.
4. **Provide example products.** If the participant does not have a specific product in mind, offer one (e.g., a battery, a packaged food item) so they can reason concretely.
5. **Explain acronyms.** Spell out SoC (Substances of Concern), LCA-EF (Life Cycle Assessment / Environmental Footprint), etc. before using them.
6. **Simplify language.** Replace “semantic gap” with “missing or mismatched data.” Avoid technical jargon unless the participant is comfortable with it.
7. **Use tables and the UI, not raw JSON.** For non-technical participants, show the DPP Preview Card or simplified tables rather than JSON snippets.
8. **Do not expect pre-reading of requirements tables.** Instead, walk through a few key requirements verbally and ask for reactions.
9. **Clarify extension origins.** Explain that extensions reference existing standards (EU Battery Regulation, REACH, GHG Protocol) but are self-defined vocabularies.
10. **Adapt based on participant profile.** For technical participants, show code and architecture. For domain experts, focus on data completeness and regulatory alignment.

1.4 Protocol Structure (50–55 min)

Phase	Duration	Content
Protocol 1: Schema & Data Model Validation		
Introduction and consent	3 min	Consent, context, thesis overview
Warm-up and knowledge assessment	4 min	Background, DPP experience, knowledge level, focus areas
Part A: Schema Design	12 min	Core boundary, extension model, field validation (adaptive)
Part B: Provenance & Trust	7 min	Provenance utility, gap categories, confidence
Protocol 2: Adoption & Implementation Evaluation		
Transition	2 min	Brief recap of Protocol 1, set context
Part C: Adoption	8 min	Barriers, enablers, linked data viability
Part D: Live Demonstration	10 min	Walk through running platform, gather reactions
Part E: Pilot Readiness	5 min	Acceptance criteria, missing requirements
Overall wrap-up	2 min	Overall assessment, final open feedback
Total	~53 min	

Table 2: Combined interview protocol structure

1.5 Requirements Baseline

The platform's 29 formal requirements (documented in `requirements-backlog.v0.csv`) are split across the two protocols. Each interview question explicitly references the requirements it validates, and the accompanying handout presents requirements tables for participant review.

Protocol 1 Requirements (Schema & Data Model — 19 requirements).

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary
SC-00	Build initial Shared Core Schema	v0.1 monolithic schema (~68 fields), validated in DSR iteration 1
SC-01	Product-agnostic schema v0.2	Minimal core (17 fields) covering identification, manufacturer, product, lifecycle
SC-02	Per-field provenance & gap reporting	Provenance per field (source, actor, confidence, conversion rule); gap reporting with severity
SC-03	Adapter lifecycle (parse-map-validate-report)	Adapter interface enforces lifecycle; initiative profiles compose core + extensions
SC-04	Core + extensions contract	Extensions compose via JSON-LD context layering; validated by test suite
EXT-01	Adapter onboarding checklist	New adapters implement <code>AdapterInterface</code> ; no core changes needed
EXT-02	Substances of Concern (SoC) extension	SoC extension: REACH/RoHS compliance, hazardous substance entries, SVHC check
EXT-03	LCA / Environmental Footprint extension	LCA-EF extension: GHG scopes, carbon footprint, lifecycle stages, impact categories
MAP-01	Mapping specification format (CSV)	Two mapping CSVs (Tractus-X 43 rows, Battery Pass 45 rows)
MAP-02	Unit conversion and normalization rules	Adapter methods handle unit conversions with conversion rules in provenance
MAP-03	Reusable transformation library	Shared helpers extracted into adapter base methods
LD-01	JSON-LD context mapping	Five JSON-LD context files mapping to Schema.org, PROV-O, QUDT, Dublin Core
LD-02	Adapter JSON-LD output	Both adapters support JSON-LD mode with embedded <code>@context</code> , <code>@id</code> , <code>@type</code>
LD-03	Triple-store integration guide	TriplyDB integration with 7 DPPs (~900 triples), loading guide
LD-04	SPARQL query demonstrations	12 SPARQL queries covering materials, carbon footprint, compliance, provenance
LD-05	Extension RDF mapping pattern	Each extension has OWL vocabulary + JSON-LD context with stable IRIs

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary
PRV-01	Provenance schema (PROV-O aligned)	Per-field provenance with source, actor, confidence; PROV-O in JSON-LD output
PRV-02	Tamper-evidence & integrity checks	Content hashing approach documented; full implementation deferred to production
EV-02	Coverage metrics & evaluation criteria	Data coverage score per module; gap reporting with populated/expected counts

Protocol 2 Requirements (Adoption & Implementation — 10 requirements).

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary
ID-01	Heterogeneous identifier input	Resolver accepts 7 ID types: UUID, GTIN, VIN, serial, MPN, DID, LGTIN
ID-02	Resolution evidence & provenance	Evidence chain with source, match type, confidence per candidate
ID-03	Candidate ranking & scoring	Candidates ranked by confidence; top candidate selected for resolution
ID-04	Identifier scheme mapping rules	Scheme-specific parsing with PREFIX_RULES, regex detection, normalization
ID-05	UPI granularity & uniqueness	Supports item-level (serial), batch-level (LGTIN), and model-level (GTIN)
API-01	OpenAPI contracts	OpenAPI 3.0.3 spec for /resolve, /normalize, /health endpoints
API-02	Example payloads & round-trip tests	7 test payloads (happy/minimal/partial-gaps); 512 automated tests
EV-01	Labeled identifier set	Evaluation dataset with known-good mappings for precision/recall testing
SEC-01	Threat-informed requirements	Documented threat model (spoofing, tampering, enumeration, DoS)
SEC-02	Anti-abuse rules	Rate-limiting placeholders; non-sequential UUIDs; production hardening documented

1.6 Ethics and Consent

- Obtain verbal informed consent at the start of each interview (confirmed on recording).
- Explain: purpose, voluntary participation, right to withdraw at any time, data handling.
- Anonymize participant identifiers in thesis (P1, P2, . . . , Pn).
- Record with permission; transcribe and code thematically (Braun & Clarke, 2006).
- Store recordings securely per institutional data management guidelines.

- No separate ethics board approval required (professional expert consultations, not human subjects research involving vulnerable populations).

2 Protocol 1: Schema & Data Model Validation

2.1 Introduction (3 min)

Interviewer Instruction

Thank you for participating. This interview is part of my master thesis on DPP interoperability. I have designed a platform that resolves heterogeneous identifiers across DPP initiatives and normalizes initiative-specific payloads into a shared core schema. The platform is fully open-source, with 512 automated tests (100% pass rate) across 22 test files, Docker Compose for single-command deployment, and a live web interface deployed on Vercel. Today we will cover two topics: first the schema design and provenance model, then adoption and a live demonstration. The full interview will take approximately 50 minutes. Your responses will be anonymized in the thesis.

2.2 Warm-Up: Participant Background and Knowledge Assessment (4 min)

Interviewer Instruction

This section helps you calibrate the rest of the interview. Depending on the participant's knowledge level, you will adapt question depth in Parts A and B. Note their focus areas for adaptive questioning later.

W1. What is your current role, and how does it relate to Digital Product Passports?

W2. Which DPP initiatives or standards have you worked with directly? (Tractus-X, Battery Pass, CIRPASS, UNTP, GS1, others)

W3. When you think about DPP data, what aspects are most important to you? For example: data completeness, regulatory compliance, supply chain traceability, environmental impact, chemical safety, or something else?

Interviewer Instruction

Use the answer to W3 to focus Parts A and B on the participant's area of expertise. If they mention chemicals, focus on SoC extension. If they mention environmental impact, focus on LCA-EF. If they mention data quality, prioritize provenance and gap reporting.

W4. Do you currently work with a specific product type that has or needs a Digital Product Passport? If so, which product?

Interviewer Instruction

If the participant does not have a specific product, offer an example: "For the purposes of our discussion, would it help to think of a specific product — say a lithium-ion battery, or a packaged food product? That way we can reason about concrete data fields."

2.3 Part A: Schema Design and Architecture (12 min)

Interviewer Instruction

*The platform uses a Shared Core Schema (v0.2) that separates product-agnostic fields from domain-specific extensions. The vocabularies are defined as five OWL ontologies hosted on GitHub Pages, each with its own JSON-LD context for Linked Data serialization. **Note:** The extensions reference existing standards (EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542, REACH, RoHS, GHG Protocol, EU PEF, EU FIC Regulation 1169/2011) but are self-defined vocabularies for this prototype.*

Current extensions:

- **Battery** (EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542): nested sub-objects for chemistry, performance, status, materials, durability, and circularity.
- **Substances of Concern, or SoC** (REACH/RoHS regulations): hazardous substance tracking and compliance.
- **Life Cycle Assessment / Environmental Footprint, or LCA-EF** (GHG Protocol, ISO 14040, EU PEF): carbon footprint, greenhouse gas emissions, lifecycle stages.
- **Food** (EU FIC Regulation 1169/2011): allergens, nutrition, origin traceability (extensibility demonstration).

Interviewer Instruction

Five initiative profiles compose core + selective extensions: Tractus-X Battery (core + battery + SoC), Battery Pass (core + battery + SoC + LCA-EF), Core-Only, Food Product (core + food), and All Extensions (testing/demo). Always point the participant to the relevant handout section.

[Show v0.2 architecture diagram: core + battery + SoC + LCA-EF + food extensions]

[Point participant to Handout Section 4 (Core Fields) — show the 17-field table]

A1. [Validates SC-00, SC-01, SC-04] I would like to start at a high level. The platform defines 17 product-agnostic core fields that apply to any Digital Product Passport, regardless of product type. Please look at Section 4 of your handout. Thinking about the products you work with, could you fill in all of these fields with your product’s information? Which fields would be straightforward, and which would be difficult or not applicable?

Probe: Are there fields you consider universally important for any product that are missing from this list?

Probe: Are any fields here that you would consider specific to certain products rather than truly cross-sector?

Interviewer Instruction

If the participant mentions “brand” as not always applicable, note this. If they question “placingOnMarket,” explain it is the date the product enters the market, relevant for lifecycle tracking. If they ask about emissions or chemicals, explain these are in the SoC and LCA-EF extensions (Section 5 of their handout).

A2. [Validates SC-03, SC-04, EXT-01, EXT-02, EXT-03] The core fields are complemented by

domain-specific extension modules. Please look at Section 5 of your handout. Based on the product you have in mind, which of these extension models would be relevant? Which would you skip?

Interviewer Instruction

First ask “which extension modules are applicable to your product?” to narrow the scope, then ask about coverage within those modules. This prevents the participant from having to evaluate all extensions.

Probe: Are there data fields you need for your product that are not covered by any of the current extensions?

Probe: Would you group any of these extensions differently — for example, would you combine Substances of Concern with the LCA-EF extension, or keep them separate?

A3. [Validates SC-00, SC-01, MAP-01] The schema evolved from version 0.1, which was a single large schema with about 68 fields focused on batteries, to version 0.2, which has a small core of 17 fields plus modular extensions for different domains. From your experience, which approach works better for supporting products across different sectors: a large, comprehensive schema or a small core with add-on modules?

Probe: What are the risks of a core that is too small versus one that is too large?

A4. [Validates SC-01, EXT-01, MAP-02, MAP-03] If we were to add support for new product types — say textiles, electronics, or construction materials — do you think the current core fields would remain stable, or would they need to change?

A5. [Validates SC-00..SC-04, EXT-01..EXT-03, MAP-01..MAP-03] I will briefly walk through a few of the key requirements that guided the design. For each one, I would like your reaction: does it seem correctly scoped, or is something missing?

Interviewer Instruction

*Do **not** ask the participant to read the full requirements table independently. Instead, select 3–5 key requirements from Section 2 of the handout that are most relevant to the participant’s domain (based on W3 responses). Walk through them verbally, explain each briefly, and ask for a reaction. For example: “One requirement is that every adapter must follow a parse-map-validate-report lifecycle. Does that make sense for how data is typically exchanged in your context?”*

Probe: Are there requirements you consider critical for DPP interoperability that are not represented here?

2.4 Part B: Provenance, Trust, and Gaps (7 min)

Interviewer Instruction

The platform tracks where each piece of data came from: which system, which adapter, what confidence level, and whether any conversions were applied. This is called “provenance.” Both JSON and JSON-LD outputs share identical provenance structure. The platform also reports when data is missing or incomplete.

Interviewer Instruction

*Adapt the presentation to the participant. For **technical participants**, show the JSON provenance example in Section 8 of Handout 1. For **domain experts**, show the DPP Preview Card on the platform UI or use the simplified provenance table in Section 8 of their handout. Avoid the term “semantic gap” — instead say “missing or mismatched data.”*

[Point participant to Handout Section 8 (Provenance Model) or show the DPP Preview Card on the live platform]

B1. [Validates PRV-01, SC-02] The platform records where each data field came from, including the source system, confidence level, and any transformations applied. Is this kind of field-level traceability useful for your organization’s decision-making or compliance requirements? Who would need to look at this information?

Probe: Is tracking the origin of each individual field the right level of detail, or would tracking at the level of the entire record be enough?

B2. [Validates SC-02, EV-02] When data cannot be fully transferred from one system to this shared schema, the platform reports the gap. We classify gaps into three types: missing fields (the source simply does not have this data), granularity mismatches (the data exists but at a different level of detail), and unit conversion conflicts (a numeric value is present but needs to be converted). Are these three categories sufficient, or are there types of mismatched data we have not considered?

Interviewer Instruction

Point participant to Section 9 (Gap Reporting) of their handout for the categorization table. For non-technical participants, explain with a concrete example: “For instance, if a battery passport from one initiative does not include recycling instructions, the platform would flag that as a missing field with medium severity.”

B3. [Validates PRV-01, PRV-02] For identifier resolution, the system assigns a confidence score to each match. What confidence level would your organization consider high enough to process automatically, versus needing a human to review?

2.5 Protocol 1 Wrap-Up

WU1. Is there anything about the schema design or provenance model that we have not covered and you consider important?

Interviewer Instruction

Thank the participant. Transition to Protocol 2: “Now I would like to shift focus to practical adoption and show you the running platform.”

3 Protocol 2: Adoption & Implementation Evaluation

3.1 Transition (2 min)

Interviewer Instruction

We have now covered the schema design and provenance model. In this second part I would like to focus on practical adoption, show you the running platform, and gather your perspective on what it would take to use this in a real-world setting. This section will take approximately 25 minutes.

R1. Before we continue, was there anything from our schema discussion that you reflected on further or would like to revisit briefly?

3.2 Part C: Adoption and Practical Considerations (8 min)

C1. [Validates SEC-01] What are the most significant barriers to DPP data exchange across organizations or initiatives in your experience?

Probe: Technical barriers (format heterogeneity, API incompatibility)?

Probe: Organizational barriers (governance, data ownership, liability)?

Probe: Regulatory barriers (timeline pressure, ambiguous requirements)?

C2. [Validates LD-01, LD-02, LD-04] The evaluation shows that SPARQL queries require 5.4× fewer lines of code than REST API implementations for cross-initiative analytics. Is linked data / JSON-LD adoption realistic in your context?

Probe: What tooling or infrastructure would be needed?

Probe: Would a dual-output approach (JSON + JSON-LD) ease the transition?

C3. [Validates EXT-01, SC-03] The platform follows an adapter pattern where adding a new initiative requires writing one adapter module (~200–400 LOC) without modifying the core. Does this extensibility model address your integration concerns?

3.3 Part D: Live Demonstration (10 min)

Interviewer Instruction

Share screen and walk through the deployed platform. Adapt the demonstration to the participant's profile:

- **For technical participants:** Show JSON output, JSON-LD output, provenance chain, SPARQL queries.
- **For domain experts:** Focus on the DPP Preview Card (visual summary), extension composition differences, and gap reporting. Use the platform's table view rather than raw JSON.

Show each capability:

1. **Identifier Resolution:** “How does your organization currently identify its products?” Then demonstrate resolving one of 7 supported ID types (UUID, GTIN, VIN, serial number, manufacturer part number, DID, LGTIN). Start with one that matches the participant's context, or use a GTIN as default.

2. **DPP Normalization:** Normalize a Tractus-X payload (JSON) and a Battery Pass payload (JSON-LD). For domain experts, show the DPP Preview Card. For technical participants, show also the raw JSON output.
3. **Extension composition:** Show how different profiles produce different extension sections (battery chemistry, SoC compliance, LCA carbon footprint). Highlight differences using the gap report.
4. **Provenance chain:** Drill into provenance for a specific field (e.g., ratedCapacity). For non-technical participants, explain as “this shows that the rated capacity value of 50 Ah came from the Tractus-X system with 95% confidence.”
5. **SPARQL Explorer:** Run a cross-initiative query on the TriplyDB knowledge graph. Show the force-directed graph visualization and table results.

Interviewer Instruction

Allow the participant to ask questions or request specific scenarios at any point.

[Open DPP Interoperability Platform UI: <https://dpp-interoperability-ui.vercel.app>]

[Show identifier resolution: resolve a GTIN, then a VIN, then a DID]

[Show JSON output vs. JSON-LD output for the same passport]

[Show SPARQL endpoint: cross-initiative query example]

D1. [Validates ID-01, API-01] Based on what you have seen, does this implementation match your expectations from our schema discussion? What surprises you, positively or negatively?

D2. [Validates API-01, API-02, LD-02] Is the platform’s output format (JSON + JSON-LD dual output) sufficient for your use case, or would additional serializations be needed (e.g., XML, CSV, XBRL)?

D3. [Validates EXT-01, SC-03, ID-04] The platform currently covers two DPP initiatives with four adapter variants (Tractus-X and Battery Pass, each in JSON and JSON-LD). If you were to integrate your initiative, what would be the most challenging aspect?

Probe: Data availability? Schema mapping complexity? Governance alignment?

3.4 Part E: Pilot Readiness and Missing Requirements (5 min)

E1. [Validates EV-01, SEC-01, SEC-02] What acceptance criteria would make this platform viable for a pilot deployment in your organization?

Probe: Performance requirements? Coverage thresholds? Integration effort?

Probe: Certification or compliance requirements?

E2. [Validates ID-01..ID-05, API-01, API-02, EV-01, SEC-01, SEC-02] Let me walk you through a few of our platform requirements—things like “the system should support multiple identifier formats” or “the API should return confidence scores.” For each one I mention, could you tell me whether it sounds right, too ambitious, or if something is missing?

Interviewer Instruction

Do NOT ask the participant to read all 10 requirements. Instead, select 3–5 requirements most relevant to their background and read them aloud one at a time. Use Handout Section 1 as your own reference. Adapt: for **technical participants**, focus on API-01, API-02, SEC-01; for **domain experts**, focus on ID-01, ID-03, EV-01. Note which requirements they flag.

Probe: Are any of these overlapping or redundant from your perspective?

Probe: Would you change the priority of any?

E3. [Validates EV-01, EV-02] If we were to prioritize the next three improvements to this platform, what would you recommend?

3.5 Overall Wrap-Up (2 min)

WU2. From your perspective, what is the most valuable aspect of this platform design? What is the weakest?

WU3. Are there any additional concerns or topics we have not discussed that you consider important for DPP interoperability?

Interviewer Instruction

Thank the participant for their time. Confirm anonymization and offer to share the thesis upon completion.

4 Data Analysis Plan

4.1 Coding Strategy

Interview transcripts will be analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke (2006):

1. **Familiarization:** Transcribe and read all interview transcripts.
2. **Initial coding:** Code responses against predefined themes:
 - Schema boundary validation (A1–A4)
 - Requirements validation (A5, E2)
 - Provenance utility (B1–B3)
 - Adoption considerations (C1–C3)
 - Implementation feedback (D1–D3)
 - Pilot readiness (E1, E3)
3. **Theme search:** Identify emergent themes not captured by predefined codes.
4. **Theme review:** Consolidate themes, check against transcripts.
5. **Theme definition:** Write thematic descriptions with representative quotes.
6. **Report:** Integrate findings into Discussion chapter.

4.2 Predefined Code Categories

4.3 Mapping Interview Findings to Design Iterations

Interview findings may trigger design iterations following the DSR build-evaluate-refine cycle:

4.4 Potential Schema Refactoring Triggers

Scenario R1: Core expansion. *Trigger:* Multiple participants identify a field as universally required but currently in an extension. *Action:* Move field from extension to core, update all adapters, re-run coverage analysis. *Impact:* Moderate (adapter updates, schema version bump to v0.3).

Scenario R2: Core contraction. *Trigger:* Participants identify a core field as product-specific. *Action:* Move field to appropriate extension, update adapters. *Impact:* Low (simplifies core, may improve coverage metrics).

Scenario R3: New extension. *Trigger:* Participants identify a domain (e.g., textiles, electronics) needing specific fields. *Action:* Create new extension vocabulary (OWL ontology + JSON-LD context), implement adapter. *Impact:* Low (additive, no core changes required).

Scenario R4: Gap taxonomy expansion. *Trigger:* Participants identify gap types not in current taxonomy. *Action:* Add gap categories to adapter reporting, update evaluation framework. *Impact:* Low (adapter output format change).

Scenario R5: Provenance simplification. *Trigger:* Participants find per-field provenance too granular. *Action:* Offer per-record or per-module provenance as configuration option. *Impact:* Low (configuration change, no architecture impact).

Code	Maps to	Description
<i>Protocol 1 — Schema & Data Model</i>		
CORE-BOUNDARY	SQ2	Core field boundary assessment
CORE-ADD	SQ2	Fields suggested for addition to core
CORE-REMOVE	SQ2	Fields suggested for removal from core
EXT-VIABLE	SQ2	Extension architecture viability
EXT-GAPS	SQ2	Missing extensions or composition issues
PROV-USEFUL	SQ3	Provenance metadata usefulness
PROV-GRANULARITY	SQ3	Provenance granularity feedback
GAP-TYPES	SQ3	Gap category completeness
TRUST-THRESHOLD	SQ3	Confidence/trust threshold expectations
<i>Protocol 2 — Adoption & Implementation</i>		
ADOPT-BARRIER	SQ5	Adoption barriers identified
ADOPT-ENABLER	SQ5	Adoption enablers identified
ADOPT-LD	SQ4	Linked data / JSON-LD feasibility assessment
IMPL-POSITIVE	SQ1	Positive implementation feedback from demo
IMPL-NEGATIVE	SQ1	Negative implementation feedback from demo
IMPL-SURPRISE	SQ1	Unexpected observations during demo
PILOT-CRITERIA	SQ5	Acceptance criteria for pilot deployment
REQ-MISSING	SQ5	Missing requirements identified
REQ-PRIORITY	SQ5	Prioritized improvements suggested
OUTPUT-FORMAT	SQ4	Output format sufficiency feedback
<i>Requirements Validation</i>		
REQ-VALID	SQ5	Requirement confirmed as correctly scoped
REQ-OVERSCOPED	SQ5	Requirement identified as too broad for prototype scope
REQ-UNDERSCOPED	SQ5	Requirement identified as insufficiently specified
REQ-MISSING-NEW	SQ5	New requirement proposed not in current backlog
REQ-REPRIORITIZE	SQ5	Requirement priority adjustment suggested

Table 5: Predefined code categories mapped to research sub-questions

Finding Type	Action
Core field addition/removal	Update schema, adapters, mappings, tests
New extension needed	Design extension vocabulary (OWL ontology + JSON-LD context), implement adapter
Provenance model change	Update provenance format, adapter outputs
New gap category	Extend gap taxonomy, update adapter reporting
Missing requirement	Add to requirements table, assess impact on architecture
Coverage threshold feedback	Calibrate evaluation criteria
Output format request	Assess serialization effort, add to backlog

Table 6: Mapping interview findings to design actions

5 Interview Materials Checklist

5.1 Materials to Prepare Before Interviews

- Consent statement (read aloud and confirmed on recording).

- One-page platform overview summary (non-technical, for screen share).
- v0.2 architecture diagram (core + 4 extensions visual).
- Core fields list with descriptions (17 fields).
- Extension vocabulary namespace table (5 OWL ontologies on GitHub Pages).
- Initiative profiles table (5 profiles: Tractus-X Battery, Battery Pass, Core-Only, Food Product, All Extensions).
- Provenance example (JSON-LD snippet with PROV-O alignment).
- Live platform access: <https://dpp-interoperability-ui.vercel.app>
- SPARQL endpoint access for live queries.
- Coverage table (Table 5.1 from evaluation chapter).
- Docker Compose ready for local demonstration backup.
- GitHub repository open: <https://github.com/JorgeRenatoLeon/Thesis-Project>
- Recording equipment and backup (e.g., Zoom/Teams recording).
- Interview schedule confirmation with participants.

5.2 Visual Aids

1. **Architecture Diagram:** Boxes showing Identifier Resolution Service (7 ID types), DPP Normalizer Service (4 adapters), Adapter Framework, Core Schema, 4 Extensions, GitHub Pages Vocabulary.
2. **Schema Diagram:** Core (17 fields) with arrows to battery (6 sub-objects: chemistry, performance, status, materials, durability, circularity), SoC (substances of concern, REACH/RoHS), LCA-EF (carbon footprint, GHG scopes), food (allergens, nutrition, origin).
3. **Provenance Example:** JSON snippet showing `ratedCapacity` field with full provenance chain (source, actor, confidence, `conversion_rule`).
4. **Coverage Table:** From evaluation chapter showing core vs. extension coverage by initiative.
5. **Repository:** <https://github.com/JorgeRenatoLeon/Thesis-Project> (open-source, 512 tests, Docker Compose).

6 Draft Practitioner Candidate List

#	Role / Profile	Organization Type	Reachability	Priority
1	DPP Technical Architect or Developer	Eclipse Tractus-X contributor or Catena-X ecosystem partner	Medium-High	High
2	Battery Passport Program Lead or Data Analyst	Global Battery Alliance or GBA Battery Passport pilot partner	Medium	High
3	CIRPASS WP Lead or Ontology Developer	CIRPASS consortium member (or CIRPASS-2 follow-up)	Medium	High
4	DPP Standards/Policy Specialist	EU standards body (EFRAG, CEN/CENELEC) or national standards institute	Low-Medium	Medium
5	Supply Chain Sustainability or Compliance Manager	Battery manufacturer, automotive OEM, or electronics producer implementing DPP	Low-Medium	Medium

6.1 Recruitment Channels

- Direct outreach via LinkedIn and open-source community contacts (GitHub, Slack).
- Supervisor and daily supervisor professional networks.
- Snowball sampling from initial participants.
- Conference and workshop contacts (e.g., HaDEA events, Catena-X community days).

Appendix: Consent Script

Interviewer Instruction

Read the following statement at the start of each interview before proceeding:

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. Before we begin, I would like to confirm the following:

1. This interview is part of my master thesis research at VU Amsterdam / UvA on interoperability in Digital Product Passports.
2. Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to answer any question or withdraw from the interview at any time without giving a reason.
3. With your permission, this interview will be audio-recorded for transcription purposes. The recording will be stored securely and deleted after the thesis is submitted and graded.
4. Your identity will be anonymized in the thesis. You will be referred to by a participant code (e.g., P1, P2).
5. The interview will take approximately 50 minutes, divided into two parts: schema validation and adoption evaluation.
6. No commercially sensitive or proprietary information is sought. If any question touches on confidential matters, please let me know and we will skip it.

Do you consent to participating in this interview and to the audio recording?

[Wait for verbal confirmation before proceeding.]